

CRM-GEOTHERMAL DELIVERABLE D3.6

REPORT ON MEMBRANE-BASED GAS EXTRACTION FROM BRINE

Summary:

In this report we present the set up to test polymeric membranes regarding their suitability to extract gas, specifically helium from geothermal brines. Membrane extraction tubes were prepared using various polymeric materials, namely polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS), polytetrafluorethylene (PTFE), Polyurethan (PU), Polyvinylchloride (PVC) and Polyethylen (PE), that are robust to harsh conditions as expected in a stream of geothermal brine. The results of batch-type experiments and field tests reveal good performance in terms of gas extraction from brine similarly for PDMS and PTFE. The envisaged helium enrichment, however, could not be approved for any material. Therefore, a two-step extraction process is proposed, where helium enrichment from the gaseous phase will be realized by enrichment via mole sieve.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Table of contents	3
Figures.....	3
1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	4
2 MEMBRANE-BASED GAS EXTRACTION FROM BRINE.....	5
2.1 Principle of gas separation by polymeric membranes	5
2.2 Laboratory experiments.....	6
2.3 Field experiment	8
3 CONCLUSION	13
4 References.....	14

FIGURES

Figure 1: Principle of gas extraction using polymers.	5
Figure 2: Prepared membrane tubing for the usage in autoclave experiments.	6
Figure 3: The autoclave that contains two membrane tubes, attached to the lid. The lid of the autoclave contains 5 gas ports that were used for feed gas flushing, membrane positioning and for permeate release. The fifth port is connected to an overpressure valve.	6
Figure 4: Gas mass spectrometer (MiniRuedi, Gasometrix GmbH) connected to the autoclave (right). Also seen is a gas bag containing reference gas for regular calibration.	7
Figure 5: Helium concentration in feed and permeate gas. Here, PDMS and PTFE membrane tubes were tested.	7
Figure 6: Set up to test the migration behaviour of helium in water.	8
Figure 7: Flow scheme of online gas measurements: (1) junction from the main production stream; (2) water meter; (3) gas water separator; (4) conventional gas separating M3 device; (5) tubular PDMS membrane; (6) tubular PTFE membrane; (7) gas meter; (8) GMIMS; (9,10) two standards in gas bags; (11) multi valve; (12) gas mass spectrometer; (13) interim water reservoir; (14) water pump; (15) bladder.....	9
Figure 8: Borehole situation during pump test.	10
Figure 9: Water-Gas ratio and production rate during the three-day pump test at GWD 001.....	11
Figure 10: Whole gas recovery with different methods. Here, direct head space sampling is compared to the commercially available GMIMS and two polymeric membranes (PTFE and PDMS) located directly in the production water.....	12
Figure 11: The He/N ₂ ratio in the production gas.....	12
Figure 12: The normalized N ₂ concentration in the production gas. It shows leakage of the PTFE membrane during the second day.....	13

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Helium (He) is a critical resource for medical and high-tech applications. Currently, it is primarily produced as a by-product of natural gas extraction, with major sources located in Qatar and the USA. In Europe, relatively high concentrations of helium have been identified in association with crystalline rocks, where nitrogen (N₂) is the dominant gas component. High levels of helium have also been detected in geothermal systems, prompting the idea of extraction of helium from geothermal fluids through membrane-based gas-water separation technology.

In laboratory batch experiments using various membrane materials, PDMS and PTFE membranes proved to be the most effective for gas extraction, offering fast response times and high diffusion efficiency. However, attempts to extract helium from a helium-enriched water phase were unsuccessful, as helium did not dissolve sufficiently in water within the necessary time frame. We assume, this is caused by the low solubility of helium in water at standard pressure and temperature condition. Due to the failure to prepare a helium-rich liquid phase, subsequent experiments were conducted in the field at a borehole site in Cornwall. There, we were able to use naturally helium-enriched geothermal water. Here the helium was added at geological time spans and at higher pressure, a prerequisite we cannot realize at lab scale.

Although the field tests were limited to three days, results demonstrated that gas separation using tubular polymeric membranes is feasible and can potentially be integrated into the continuous production cycle of geothermal fluids. However, helium enrichment in the extracted gas phase was not achieved. Consequently, our work plan was adjusted to explore secondary helium enrichment directly from the extracted gas using molecular sieves.

In the final phase of the project, we are testing a two-step helium extraction process:

Gas-Water Separation: Free and dissolved gases in the geothermal brine are extracted using membrane gas separation. Tubular membranes are inserted into a bypass line, allowing gas extraction without interrupting the ongoing pumping process.

Helium Enrichment: The extracted nitrogen-dominated gas, which contains minor amounts of water vapor, CO₂, and helium, is further processed to increase helium concentration. Water vapor and CO₂ are removed using cryogenic methods, such as trapping in liquid nitrogen. Additional enrichment is achieved by removing N₂ with titanium getter sponges or specialized molecular sieves. This step is designed as a cyclic process to incrementally raise the helium concentration.

Laboratory testing of the secondary enrichment techniques is ongoing to evaluate their performance and efficiency.

2 MEMBRANE-BASED GAS EXTRACTION FROM BRINE

According to Halford et al. (2022), natural gas containing more than 0.3% helium is considered economically viable for extraction. However, as Hamedi et al. (2019) emphasize, helium production must be seamlessly integrated into existing extraction processes to avoid operational disruptions. In this context, the CRM-Geothermal project aimed to evaluate the feasibility of using robust and durable tubular membrane materials that could be incorporated directly into geothermal production streams. The goal was to develop a simple, cost-effective gas extraction solution that operates without interrupting ongoing geothermal fluid production. To this end, several commercially available tubular membrane materials were selected for initial testing, including polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS), polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), polyurethane (PU), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), and polyethylene (PE).

2.1 Principle of gas separation by polymeric membranes

Polymeric membranes are materials capable of selectively separating different fluids, allowing certain components to pass through while blocking others. This separation process, driven by concentration gradients, is known as membrane gas separation and is commonly used to extract gases from liquids (Figure 1). The separation operates via a three-step solution-diffusion mechanism: (1) gas molecules dissolve into the membrane material, (2) diffuse through it, and (3) desorb on the opposite side.

Figure 1: Principle of gas extraction using polymers.

When tubular membranes are used, the tubes are inserted directly into the feed mixture—comprising both water and gas. The permeated gas is collected inside the tubing, where it can be transported for further analysis or processing. Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of this method in separating gas mixtures through the selective permeability of different membrane materials (e.g., Collins and Ghosh, 2017).

As part of the CRM-geothermal project, the feasibility of gas separation from geothermal brine was investigated, with a particular focus on evaluating the selectivity of various membranes for helium.

2.2 Laboratory experiments

For the envisaged experiments in an autoclave set ups, the tubular material was prepared with two end fittings to be compatible with conventional stainless-steel fittings (Figure 2). The length of the membrane was selected based on the dimensions of the autoclave, with

Figure 2: Prepared membrane tubing for the usage in autoclave experiments.

a total length of 20 cm. To prevent collapse during the experiment, the tubes were filled with glass beads. One end of each tube was sealed, while the other was connected to the autoclave lid (Figure 3) to allow the extracted gas (permeate) to be directed to the adjacent gas mass spectrometer (Figure 4) for analysis. The experiments were conducted at ambient pressure and temperature conditions.

Figure 3: The autoclave that contains two membrane tubes, attached to the lid. The lid of the autoclave contains 5 gas ports that were used for feed gas flushing, membrane positioning and for permeate release. The fifth port is connected to an overpressure valve.

Figure 4: Gas mass spectrometer (MiniRuedi, Gasometrix GmbH) connected to the autoclave (right). Also seen is a gas bag containing reference gas for regular calibration.

A typical result from such an experiment is shown in Figure 5. The autoclave was initially assembled with ambient air and then continuously flushed with an artificial gas mixture containing 0.5% helium. An immediate increase in helium concentration was observed in the permeate gas, with equilibrium between the feed and permeate gases being reached within five hours.

Figure 5: Helium concentration in feed and permeate gas. Here, PDMS and PTFE membrane tubes were tested.

The size-selective properties of the membranes, as described by Wang et al. (2019), were not reproducible with the material used in this study. Given the atomic diameter of helium (0.255 nm), which is the smallest compared to other gases such as hydrogen (0.289 nm), carbon dioxide (0.33 nm), nitrogen (0.364 nm), and methane (0.38 nm), we would expect some differentiation in diffusion behaviour. However, our experiments revealed a uniform diffusion pattern across all gases, with no significant selectivity observed.

Figure 6: Set up to test the migration behaviour of helium in water.

As we could not prepare a brine containing helium in the water phase, lab experiments focussing on dissolved helium and its extraction via membrane could not adequately be performed. However, this type of experiments was done during a pump test using naturally helium-enriched water at the Cornish Lithium Limited site in Cornwall.

A further series of experiments was conducted to assess the migration behaviour of dissolved helium through water as an intermediate diffusion medium. For these experiments, the autoclave was fitted with two additional reservoirs: one filled with pure helium ("ALL") and the other with ambient air ("NONE"), see Figure 6. In the baseline experiment, without any water filling, equilibrium between the two reservoirs was reached in approximately 6 hours. However, when water was used as the diffusion medium, no equilibrium was achieved even after 15 days, indicating that the migration of helium through water is much slower.

This suggests that fluids in helium-rich reservoirs may require prolonged residence times to achieve significant helium concentrations. Therefore, enhanced helium recovery through water circulation is not a viable technique for helium production.

2.3 Field experiment

A field campaign was conducted between 20/06/2023 and 07/07/2023 in collaboration with Cornish Lithium Limited (CLL) at the United Downs site in southwest England, UK, to test the suitability of membrane materials under real-world conditions. The test site featured a borehole (GWDD-001) that penetrates fractured metamorphic and granitic

rocks. The borehole reaches a measured depth (MD) of 1098 m, is uncased below approximately 200 m (MD), and has a diameter of about 89 mm (at the time of drilling). The borehole intersects two steeply dipping fractures between 600 and 700 m (MD), which, based on previous testing and borehole logging by CLL, were identified as highly conducive to fluid flow.

Gas measurements were performed during a pump test on GWDD-001. The flow scheme of the gas extraction unit is shown in Figure 7. The unit was fed from a junction (1) connected to the main fluid stream produced by the borehole pump, which passed through a regulation valve to adjust the flow rate for a continuous, stable volume regime. The stream was then divided into two parts. One portion passed through a water meter (2) before entering the gas-water separator (3), where three membranes were installed in direct connection with the water stream for experimental purposes.

Additionally, the headspace (4) containing the degassed water was sampled for comparison. A conventional gas-separating membrane (3M Liqui-Cel™ MM Series Membrane Contactors, G591, 5x1) was used to prevent humidity from entering the measurement system. In the water phase of the gas-water separator, two types of tubular polymer membranes (PTFE and PDMS) were employed (5,6) to test their ability to extract and enrich helium from the liquid phase into the gas phase. As the fluid passed through the separator, the gas phase was released into the headspace, where it passed through a gas meter (7) to quantify the gas release. Using the data from the gas and water meters, the gas-water ratio of the production fluid could be determined (Figure 9).

Figure 7: Flow scheme of online gas measurements: (1) junction from the main production stream; (2) water meter; (3) gas water separator; (4) conventional gas separating M3 device; (5) tubular PDMS membrane; (6) tubular PTFE membrane; (7) gas meter; (8) GMIMS; (9,10) two standards in gas bags; (11) multi valve; (12) gas mass spectrometer; (13) interim water reservoir; (14) water pump; (15) bladder.

The second portion of the flow entered a conventional gas-water separating membrane (7; GMIMS) for subsequent gas analysis. Using a multi-valve system (11), extracted gas samples from the headspace, membrane tubes, and GMIMS were continuously measured

with a portable mass spectrometer (12; miniRUEDI, Gasometric GmbH, Switzerland). The fluid flow was collected in an interim container (13) before being pumped (14) into a bladder (15), where it was temporarily stored for subsequent experiments.

The test work consisted of three days of pumping, with the fluid being of low salinity and temperatures ranging from 20°C to 28°C. Two distinct phases of sampling were conducted, during which the casing position—and consequently, the sampling conditions—changed (Figure 8). In Phase One, the rig was positioned at a depth greater than 1000 m, producing only the lower fluid flow. In Phase Two, the rig was adjusted to a depth of less than 600 m, allowing both fluid flow zones to be targeted for sampling.

Figure 8: Borehole situation during pump test.

During Phase 1, where only the lower fluid flow zone (1000 m depth) was targeted, the production rate was 13 L/min, with approximately 1 L of gas present in 20–30 L of produced water. In Phase 2, with both fluid flow zones (600 m and 1000 m) producing, the production rate increased to 57 L/min. However, the gas content in 70–80 L of produced water remained approximately 1 L of gas (Figure 9). Since the gas volume did not increase when both fluid flow zones were sampled, it suggests that the gas-rich fluids primarily originate from the lower fluid flow zone.

Figure 9: Water-Gas ratio and production rate during the three-day pump test at GWD 001.

We utilized a commercially available membrane (GMIMS) as well as PDMS and PTFE tubular polymeric membranes, which had been pre-tested in laboratory experiments. Additionally, the headspace of the gas-water separator was analysed. As shown in Figure 9, the separation performance of the membranes varied. We believe that technical issues, such as leakage and pressure effects, may have contributed to these discrepancies. During a stable production phase, between 1000 and 1400 minutes elapsed time, the results from all extraction methods showed good agreement. The gas concentrations were consistent across methods, suggesting that polymeric tubular membranes are a feasible alternative to conventional gas extractors (Figure 10).

Stable conditions were achieved during Phase 1 on 21/05/2023 (Figure 10). Analysis of the permeate gas composition revealed no helium enrichment in any of the membranes tested (Figure 11). Initially, the PTFE membrane appeared to exhibit selectivity for nitrogen over helium. However, a closer inspection of the normalized nitrogen values (Figure 12) indicates that the PTFE membrane experienced leakage during this time period, with lower nitrogen values likely caused by dilution with ambient air.

Figure 10: Whole gas recovery with different methods. Here, direct head space sampling is compared to the commercially available GMIMS and two polymeric membranes (PTFE and PDMS) located directly in the production water.

Figure 11: The He/N₂ ratio in the production gas.

Figure 12: The normalized N₂ concentration in the production gas. It shows leakage of the PTFE membrane during the second day.

The three days of field testing were instrumental in demonstrating the suitability of the polymeric tubular membranes. While issues related to leakage and pressure differences were encountered and successfully addressed, a longer experimental run would be beneficial to establish a more reliable and stable setup.

3 CONCLUSION

Gas separation using polymeric membranes from brines has been successfully established through both laboratory and field experiments. While laboratory tests demonstrated effective gas separation, the preparation of helium-rich liquids could not be achieved. Consequently, these experiments were transitioned to field tests at Cornish Lithium Ltd., where the suitability of the gas-water separation method was successfully verified. The field testing, conducted in collaboration with Cornish Lithium Limited at the United Downs site, confirmed the potential of polymeric tubular membranes for gas extraction from geothermal fluids. It was observed that the lower fluid flow zone (1000 m depth) was the primary source of gas-rich fluids. Both PDMS and PTFE membranes, as well as conventional gas-water separators, showed promising performance in whole gas extracting.

However, technical challenges, such as leakage and pressure differences, were encountered and addressed during the testing. Although the 3-day experimental period provided valuable insights, a longer testing duration would be crucial to further stabilize the system and enhance the reliability of the setup.

In conclusion, the application of polymeric tubular membranes for gas extraction proves to be feasible. The option of direct integration into the running production stream, as well as the cost efficient set up offers distinct advantages over conventional methods. Nonetheless, further optimization, including longer-term testing, is necessary to fully assess the efficiency and performance of the system in real-world conditions.

Ongoing tests focused on improving helium yield are currently underway, with efforts to implement a second step of helium enrichment through nitrogen removal using molecular sieves.

4 REFERENCES

Colin A. Scholes, C.A., Ghosh, U.K., 2017: Review of Membranes for Helium Separation and Purification. *Membranes* 7, 9, doi:10.3390/membranes7010009

Halford, D.T., Karolytè, R., Barry, P.H., Whyte, C.J., Darrah, Cuzella, T.H. , Sonnenberg, S.A., Ballentine, C.J, 2022: High helium reservoirs in the Four Corners area of the Colorado Plateau, USA. *Chemical Geology*, Vol 596, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2022.120790>.

Hamedi, H., Karimi I.A., Gundersen, T., 2019: Optimization of helium extraction processes integrated with nitrogen removal units: A comparative study. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, Volume 121, 354-366, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compchemeng.2018.11.002>

Wang, X., Shan, M., Liu, X., Wang, M., Doherty, C.M., Osadchii, D., Kapteijn, F., 2019: High-Performance Polybenzimidazole Membranes for Helium Extraction from Natural Gas *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 11 (22), 20098-20103, doi: 10.1021/acsami.9b05548